

CHARACTERISTICS OF HIGH-PROTEIN NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT IN CERVICAL CANCER POSTOPERATIVE PATIENTS.

Khudayberdiyeva Shohista Amirkul kizi

Basic doctoral student Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14575024>

As for now, treatment for cervical cancer mainly consists of surgical intervention, supplemented with radiotherapy, chemotherapy, targeted therapy, etc. Metabolic disorders are common in patients undergoing treatment for malignant tumors. Malnutrition and metabolic problems reduce the body's resistance to anti-tumor therapy, increase the risk of side effects of anti-tumor therapy, and affect quality of life. Therefore enhancing nutritional risk screening and effective nutritional support for cervical cancer patients is of great clinical importance.

However, the effect of nutritional support on patients during the postoperative treatment period is currently not well studied. Therefore, in this study, we retrospectively analyzed the clinical records of cervical cancer patients and examined the effect of standard nutritional support therapy on postoperative course and quality of life.

In recent years, with advances in cancer diagnosis and treatment, nutritional indicators have come to have important value in cancer treatment. A meta-analysis has shown that nutritional status is an important factor influencing the prognosis of glioma patients.

Objective: To comparatively investigate the impact of standard nutritional support based on nutritional risk screening on the nutritional status and quality of life of postoperative cervical cancer patients.

Materials and methods: The clinical data of 67 patients with RSM treated at the Samarkand branch of the Republican Specialized Center of Oncology and Radiology between February 2021 and February 2023 were retrospectively investigated. Routine nutritional support (control): Patients received standard doses of enteral and parenteral nutritional support, energy requirements of 20 kcal/kg, protein requirements of 1.1 g/kg/day, and the duration of nutritional intervention It did not exceed 5 days. Protein saturation group (main group): Patients received standard doses of enteral and parenteral nutrition supporting energy requirements of 30 kcal/kg and protein requirements of 1.5-2.0 g/kg/day for the duration of the nutritional intervention. was as follows. 6 days. Primary evaluation parameters: albumin (ALB), total protein (TP), and hemoglobin (Hb) were compared before surgery, on the morning of the next day after surgery, and the morning of the 14th day after surgery. Secondary

endpoints: He compared readmission rates, tumor recurrence rates, and mortality rates 6 months after discharge between the two groups.

Results:

35 (52.2%) patients with SCM who received routine nutritional support postoperatively were included in the control group, and the remaining 32 (47.8%) patients who received protein-rich nutritional support postoperatively were included in the main group. There were no notable differences between the two groups in age $39.5 \pm 5.2 / 41.12 \pm 3.9$ $p=0.31$ (control group/main group, respectively), BMI (kg/m²) $20.1 \pm 1.19 / 21.6 \pm 1.78$, $p=0.388$, tumor localization $p=0.874$, tumor diameter $p=0.235$, differentiation level $p=0.513$, (all $P > 0.05$).

Before the implementation of nutritional intervention, there were no notable variances observed in the levels of ALB, OB, and HB (all $P > 0.05$) between the two groups. However, following 14 days post-surgery, it was evident that the levels of ALB, OB, and HB were notably elevated in the primary group compared to the control group. These differences were found to be statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), indicating a positive impact of the intervention on the nutritional status of the main group. The main group exhibited lower PG-SGA scores compared to the control group at both the 60-day and 90-day post-surgery marks, with a significant intergroup effect ($F=10.081$, $P=0.004$).

Additionally, there was a trend of decreasing PG-SGA scores in both groups over time, as indicated by a time effect ($F=74.31$). 2. In the logistic regression model, efficacy (0=good, 1=poor) was utilized as the dependent variable, while various measures of statistical significance served as independent variables. The analysis revealed that age emerged as an independent factor influencing the efficacy of nutritional support in postoperative RSM patients, as detailed in Table 3.

Group	Events	Re-hospitalization	Tumor recurrence	Mortality
Control group	35	10 (28.6%)	6 (17.1%)	2 (5,7%)
Main group	32	9 (28,1%)	3 (9,4%)	1(3,1%)
<i>P</i>		0.411	0.032 1	0.168

An examination of multiple variables influencing the effectiveness of nutritional assistance in individuals diagnosed with glioma was conducted through statistical analysis.

Factors	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>OR (95% CI)</i>
Age	0.489	0.165	7.301	0.006	1.599 (1.155-2.401)
IIMT	-0.902	0.732	1.605	0.211	0.401 (0.094-1.671)
Tumor diameter	0.566	0.901	0.421	0.548	1.766 (0.310-10.232)
Tumor differentiation	0.499	0.987	0.266	0.620	1.665 (0.245-11.718)

Conclusion: In conclusion, the results suggest that implementing a high-protein nutritional intervention based on nutritional risk screening can be beneficial for patients with RSM. This intervention can help improve their postoperative nutritional status and quality of life, while also reducing the risk of postoperative tumor recurrence. It is crucial to conduct nutritional risk screening in patients with RRMS and provide them with appropriate nutritional support. It is worth noting that elderly patients only experience an improvement in protein balance at very high protein intakes. Due to their higher catabolism and anabolic resistance, it is recommended to provide them with 2-2.5 g/kg protein per day. On the other hand, younger patients do not significantly increase protein synthesis beyond 1.5 g/kg protein intake.

Literature:

1. Bingham S.A. et al. // Lancet. — 2003. — Vol. 361. — P. 1496–1501.
2. Riboli E., Norat T. // Am. J. Clin. Nutr. — 2003. — Vol. 78, Suppl. — P. 559–569.
3. Dem Krebs keine Chance / Red. H. Bohnenkamp, M.C. Schachl. — Frankfurt am Main: Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft e. V., 2000. — 34 S.
4. Bozzetti F., Gavazzi C., Cozzaglio et al. Total parenteral nutrition and tumour growth in malnourished patients with gastric cancer // Tumori. — 1999. — Vol. 85, № 3. — P. 163–166.
5. Warren S. The immediate causes of death in cancer // Am. J. Med. Sci. — 1932. — Vol. 184. — P. 610–615.
6. Fearon K.C., Preston T. Body composition in cancer cachexia // Infusionstherapie. — Basel, 1990. — Vol. 17, Suppl. 3. — P. 63–66